

CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS ENCOUNTERED BY G10-AGONCILLO LEARNERS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING AT TAAL NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

Modular Distance Learning offered a brand-new avenue in the education industry since the pandemic started. Amidst COVID-19 pandemic, DepEd ensured the continuity of learning through MDL-Self Learning Modules based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies. However, on the first few months of its implementation, several concerns were observed. Some of these were learners' concerns. In order to address these concerns, this research was conducted to determine the challenges and barriers that G10 - Agoncillo learners from Taal NHS had encountered due to the implementation of Modular Distance Learning. The descriptive method of research was used. A research-made questionnaire was used to gather data necessary for the study. The data collected were analyzed and statistically interpreted to support the identified questions. The researcher made use of frequency count, weighted mean and ranking to explain the data gathered. The results of the study revealed that respondents considered "Poor Time Management" as one of their greatest challenges encountered. Moreover, the researchers found out that the respondents have series of solutions to the identified challenges and thus ranked them from the most relevant to least relevant. The study further revealed that a series of suggested activities may help learners address their challenges and barriers properly thus accomplishing their MDL-SLM properly. The researchers recommended that a.) learners should proceed with their suggested solutions to overcome the challenges they encountered, specifically on time management, self-motivation and learning focus b) parents and guardians should actively support the school in the execution of MDL-SLM by facilitating learning at home c) content writers and teachers should always consider learners' diversity and needs and d) identified challenges and barriers should be addressed properly to help improve learner's performance.

Keywords: Action Research, Modular Distance Learning, Descriptive Method, Research Made Questionnaire, Philippines- Southeast Asia